

Impact Factor: 4.917

ISSN: 2181-0966

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0966

www.tadqiqot.uz

JOURNAL OF

ORAL MEDICINE AND CRANIOFACIAL RESEARCH

Informing scientific practices around the world through research and development

SAMARKAND
STATE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY

VOLUME 5
ISSUE 2

2024

ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF ORAL MEDICINE AND CRANIOFACIAL RESEARCH

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

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JOURNAL OF ORAL MEDICINE AND CRANIOFACIAL RESEARCH

№2 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0966-2024-2>

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RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE INCIDENCE OF COMPLICATIONS IN MANDIBULAR THIRD MOLARS EXTRACTION (LITERATURE REVIEW)

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12531312>

ANNOTATION

One of the questions of dentistry that has no unambiguous solution is the question of the attitude to third molars. It is conditioned by a number of objective circumstances. Firstly, the existing opinion about the inferiority of third molars as rudimentary structures. This point of view is held not only by many practicing dentists, but also by well-known representatives of domestic and foreign dental science.

Keywords: retrospective analysis, third molars, mandible

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РЕТРОСПЕКТИВНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ЧАСТОТЫ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ ПРИ УДАЛЕНИИ ТРЕТЬИХ МОЛЯРОВ НИЖНЕЙ ЧЕЛЮСТИ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Одним из вопросов стоматологии, не имеющим однозначного решения, является вопрос об отношении к третьим молярам. Обусловлено это рядом объективных обстоятельств. Во-первых, существующим мнением о неполноценности третьих моляров как рудиментарных структур. Этой точки зрения придерживаются не только многие стоматологи-практики, но и известные представители отечественной и зарубежной стоматологической науки.

Ключевые слова: ретроспективный анализ, третьи моляры, нижняя челюсть

Asqarov Mansur Anvarovich
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PASTKI JAG'NING UCHINCHI MOLARLARINI OLIB TASHLASHDA ASORATLAR PAYDO BO'LISHINING RETROSPEKTIV TAHLILI (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

АННОТАТСИЯ

Stomatologiyaning aniq echimi bo'lmagan savollaridan biri bu uchinchi molarlarga bo'lgan munosabat masalasidir. Bu bir qator ob'ektiv holatlarga bog'liq. Birinchidan, uchinchi molarlarning ibtidoiy tuzilmalar sifatida pastligi haqidagi mavjud fikr. Ushbu nuqtai nazarga nafaqat ko'plab stomatologlar, balki mahalliy va xorijiy stomatologiya fanining taniqli vakillari ham amal qilishadi.

Kalit so'zlar: retrospektiv tahlil, uchinchi molarlar, pastki jag

Introduction. In different clinical studies, the probability of post-extraction lesions of the inferior alveolar nerve varies from 0.35% to 19% depending on the location of the third lower molar and the chosen extraction technique. The importance of adequate visualization of anatomical structures at the treatment planning stage in dentistry is due to the unpredictable clinical outcome of dental interventions. During surgery for the removal of third

molars, a bilateral anatomical structure may be damaged, namely the mandibular canal with a neurovascular bundle consisting of the inferior alveolar nerve, the artery and vein of the same name[6].

According to K. A. Egorov, S. V. Grishin, and K. A. Korotkov (2007), the course of the mandibular canal is described as a descending line, and in the body of the mandible as a

sinusoid, which in the area of molar roots makes a bend with a downward bulge. Therefore, correct visualization of the canal inside the mandible at the stage of planning and making a clinical decision on the surgical treatment of the third molar allows to avoid one of the complications - perforation of the wall of the mandibular canal with damage to all elements of the neurovascular bundle. Currently, in our Republic, scheduled surgical interventions (complete extraction) are used for the extraction of mandibular third molars, with the help of which a high percentage of cure rate is achieved [7].

Greater technical difficulties in the treatment of complicated forms of caries of third molars compared to other teeth. Thirdly, the small participation of third molars in the realization of masticatory function in intact tooth rows. Thus, N.I. Agapov, who proposed a system for evaluating the decrease in chewing efficiency after the loss of individual teeth, did not consider third molars at all. According to I.M. Oxman [2], the specific contribution of each of the lower third molars to the realization of masticatory function is 4%, and each upper third molar - 3%. Unpredictability of spontaneous uncomplicated eruption of lower third molars in their inclined position. The possibility of unfavorable influence of third molars on the formation of the dentoalveolar apparatus, leading to the development of bite anomalies, deformation of dental rows [4].

Sixthly, the occurrence of a number of diseases pathogenetically associated with third molars: pericoronitis, periostitis, osteomyelitis, lymphadenitis, abscess, phlegmon, caries of the second molar, follicular and peri-root cysts, ameloblastoma [5].

The totality of these provisions often serves as a justification for refusing to treat uncomplicated and especially complicated forms of caries and justifying the expansion of indications for the removal of intact third molars in order to prevent the development of dentoalveolar anomalies, deformities, and the emergence of complications of infectious-inflammatory nature. How well reasoned is this approach? To answer this question, not only a comprehensive analysis of the situation in a particular patient is important, but also a balanced assessment of the evidence for each of the above provisions used as arguments in favor of expanding the indications for the removal of third molars.

The entire variety of clinical manifestations of complicated HTM eruption can be classified according to the pathogenetic principle:

- infectious-inflammatory complications
- neoplastic complications
- destruction of the hard tissues of the second molar
- occurrence of bite disorders.

Retention, formation of bite abnormalities and deformation of dental rows occupy a special place among the complications of HTM eruption. This is due to the fact that the occurrence of these complications is due to the peculiarities of the laying, development and formation of tissues of the facial skeleton. In fact, there are three outcomes of the same process. Retention is the most favorable outcome, as it is not actually a pathological process, but a pathological condition, i.e. a deviation from the norm that exists for a long time, but does not adversely affect the health of the organism.

In adolescence, the development and eruption of HTM may stimulate excessive longitudinal growth of the mandible. This may result in the formation of a mesial bite. [3].

Atkinson S. It confirms that the pressure developed by HTM during eruption can cause excessive eruption of the seventh tooth

with the formation of an open bite in the anterior part. Confirmation of this theory is the data obtained showing that when the third molars erupt, the depth of the incisor overlap decreases.

At an older age, erupting HTMS develop such strong pressure on the surrounding tissues that they cause the teeth in front of them to shift in the mesial direction. Result: formation of a close position of the teeth — violations of the position of several teeth (vestibular-oral deviation, cake-anomalies) without deformation of the apical arch. With a further increase in the shortage of space, a crowded position of the teeth occurs — deformation of the apical arch due to dystopia of one or more teeth.

In the presence of malocclusion and deformities of the dentition, the quality of chewing food deteriorates, respiratory indicators deteriorate, the erasability of individual teeth increases, periodontal diseases progress, an aesthetic defect appears [8].

At the same time, there is no consensus among doctors regarding the "HTM problem". The recommendations of various authors are sometimes diametrically opposed: from the longest possible wait-and-see tactics to the earliest possible "preventive" removal of the beginnings of HTM. The opposition of opinions and the rejection of other points of view make it difficult for communication and mutual understanding between doctors, which ultimately affects patients.

Differences in the choice of therapeutic tactics in relation to HTM are determined by a discrepancy in views on the mechanism of their eruption and the causes of retention. Some authors believe that due to the evolutionary reduction of the jaws caused by the predominance of soft-consistency food in the diet of modern humans, teeth are reduced, and HTM is a rudimentary organ [5]. Other authors, based on the fact that the HTM size does not decrease during evolution, reject this theory [1].

Currently, there are many theories of HTM eruption delay mechanisms, which are usually grouped into the following groups.

1. Theories explaining retention by a lack of space in the dental arch.
2. Theories of embryonic developmental disorder of the HTM germ, leading to tooth dystopia.
3. Theories of polyethological effects, as a result of which there is a delay in the development of the mandible.
4. Theories of countering the eruption of HTM pathologically altered mucous membrane of the retromolar region.
5. Theories of displacement of the HTM rudiment due to the activity of the germinal zone of the mandible located in the area of its angle. Bending, the angle of the lower jaw drags the root part of the tooth with it.

The following fact attracts special attention to the treatment of complicated HTM eruption. The removal of retarded HTMS is one of the rather complex operations due to a number of circumstances:

- 1) significant injury to the tissues surrounding the tooth;
- 2) difficulties or impossibility of using anatomical forceps due to an anomaly in the position of the tooth;
- 3) severe course of the postoperative period: severity of reactive postoperative phenomena, deterioration of quality of life, temporary disability;
- 4) high risk of both intraoperative and postoperative complications.

Thus, the study of the HTM eruption process, related changes in the facial skeleton and dentition, as well as the improvement

of the procedure for the removal of a retentive tooth are relevant.
I

The choice of the method of extraction of the lower third molars depends on the location in the jaw, proximity to important anatomical formations. Surgery with the preservation of the integrity of important anatomical structures can be performed both on an outpatient basis and in a hospital. However, this can be achieved under certain conditions: removal of the lower third molars with a relatively distant location from the lower alveolar canal with united roots. In modern conditions, when patients demand a rapid rehabilitation process and preservation of the integrity of anatomical structures throughout treatment and after, some modifications of the classical stages of surgery are required. Retention and dystopia of the third molars of the mandible with a close location of the roots to the inferior alveolar nerve is a common pathology among young and middle-aged people, traumatic removal of such teeth can lead to formidable complications not only of a purulent-inflammatory nature, but also neuralgic. Such injuries directly lead to a functional loss of sensory sensitivity in the area of the lower lip, cheek, chin, tongue, and in this regard, there are violations of oral speech, difficulties with eating and fluids. Consequently, there are serious prerequisites for traumatic damage to these areas. The incidence of temporary paraesthesia varies from 0.4 to 9.4%, but long-term sensory impairment is less than 1%. At first glance, the frequency of such complications is quite low, but, as practice shows, they have serious consequences that significantly reduce the quality of life. Some risk factors for complications increase dramatically in the presence of "close" contact between the roots of the third molars and the mandibular canal.

In turn, one of the existing methods of treatment, such as the complete removal of the third molar of the mandible under difficult anatomical conditions, does not fully satisfy specialists today. Therefore, the issues of their diagnosis and treatment remain in the spotlight, and the relevance of research aimed at finding and developing new methods of diagnosis, surgical treatment and their socio-economic significance are obvious.

The peculiarities of the location of the roots of the third molars of the mandible (the close location of the roots to the inferior alveolar nerve, the "embrace" of the latter, well-developed blood supply and innervation) determine the general characteristics of a potential postoperative injury. In turn, the extraction of the third molars of the mandible is accompanied by tissue infiltration and inflammatory edema, pain in the area of surgery, the development of inflammatory contracture of the masticatory muscles, often, as indicated above, complications are not only inflammatory, but also neurological in nature.

Conclusions: Taking this into account, along with performing the necessary surgical intervention, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory therapy is carried out in order to prevent and treat complications. However, the ever-increasing arsenal of medications used after the removal of the third molars of the mandible does not always lead to the desired result. The search for new effective methods of surgical treatment that prevent the development of complications is one of the urgent problems of maxillofacial surgery and surgical dentistry. In turn, there is a growing interest in minimally invasive treatment methods not only from specialists, but also from patients.

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ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF ORAL MEDICINE AND CRANIOFACIAL RESEARCH
VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

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